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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this document is to create two life cycle models, on which develop and test the future design of the current limiter device.

The first model is created to evaluate the social risks arising from the value chain of producing the InSb-Printed Circuit Board (PCB) that will be part of the final Current Limiter device, whilst the second model is an LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) one focusing on the environmental impacts arising from the production of the Novetrol PCB.

Deliverable leader:	SPL
Contributors:	Martina Pucciarelli (SPL)
Reviewers:	Mihaela Albu (UPB), Mina Gheamalinga (ACT)
Approved by:	UPB

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DEFINITIONS, ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym/ Abbreviation	Title
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
CTU	Comparative Toxic Unit
DALY	Disability Adjusted Life Year
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
S-LCA	Social-Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life cycle inventory
LCIA	Life cycle impact assessment
S-LCI	Social-Life cycle inventory
S-LCIA	Social -Life cycle impact assessment
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
JRC	Joint Research Center
ISO	International Standardization Organization
DC	Direct-Current
CL	Current Limiter
FU	Functional unit
GWP	Global Warming Potential
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
PSILCA	Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment
MRIO	Multi-regional Input Output
PV	Photovoltaic
EF	Environmental Footprint
LCT	Life Cycle Thinking

INTRODUCTION

DELIVERABLE OVERVIEW AND OBJECTIVES

The deliverable 5.2 “Standard [Sustainability] Life Cycle Model Development” focuses on the application of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) methodologies and their integration to estimate both the environmental performance and social risks associated with the current limiter device. The objectives are to identify a first-pilot study, identify and define an approach to carry out both LCA and S-LCA; start the first round of data collection (representative of the state of the project at the current date); creation of a first LCA model and of a first S-LCA model to be employed within the NOVETROL project, and improved going ahead with the project.

DOCUMENT FRAMEWORK

The document presents a first case study concerning the application of the S-LCA methodology to the current limiter manufacturing phase, as well as its environmental impacts evaluated throughout the LCA methodology.

OVERALL METHOD: PROSPECTIVE LIFE CYCLE THINKING

NOVETROL project has the main objective of creating a new technology and to increase its technology readiness level (TRL). Therefore, when applying both the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) methodologies, the data collection would provide data representative for laboratory productions, and not for pilot or industrial scales. Results representative of lab-scale production are useful to identify hot-spots and understand issues that are linked to that specific production scale. A prospective approach is defined as a systematic way to explore the potential development of a production system at a certain time in the future. Therefore, it is an explorative approach that tries to define the development of a foreground and background system (production system) to go from a lab-scale production of a low TRL technology/product to an industrial-scale production of a high TRL product. This entails an upscale of the production system and an upgrade in terms of production technologies. Employment of a prospective approach would be useful to understand the environmental impacts associated with a pilot or industrial scale when the technology reaches a higher TRL.

Based on this definition and the objective of this deliverable, which is the development of a life cycle model to assess the environmental and social performances of NOVETROL

technology, it has been decided to attempt to employ a prospective approach for both the LCA and S-LCA studies. Application of the prospective approach to both studies will also provide methodological consistency, which is fundamental for the integration of results required in D5.3 “Decision making model development and first pilot test”.

Figure 1 Graphical illustration of prospective LCA across TRL and time (Hasnaningrum H., 2025).

Moreover, in this case study we propose the application of the prospective approach to both LCA and S-LCA studies; this will have an impact, especially on the data collection and inventory phase. The data employed in both studies needs to be the same, aligned. The consistency needs to be at both quality levels, i.e. geographically and temporally. Knowing the geographical location of both background and foreground systems is a *sine-qua-non* condition for carrying S-LCA studies, whilst for LCA studies the lack of this information can be overcome. Starting from this constraint, it has been decided to start the sustainability assessment from the S-LCA study that entails the identification of possible suppliers, in terms of the most probable suppliers and their locations. This piece of information, together with others, is then used in the subsequent LCA study, as proposed in (Pucciarelli, 2023).

CASE STUDY DEFINITION – GOAL AND SCOPE

This deliverable focuses on defining and trying out the proposed prospective life cycle thinking approach, starting from an S-LCA study and then moving to an LCA one, aiming at defining a standard sustainability life cycle model for the NOVETROL project.

In this specific case, the model and results represent the status quo of the project at the moment when data were collected and the study was carried out, which means evaluation of the Printed Circuit Board (PCB) representing the core technology of the current limiter (CL) device. Once the data will be available, the study will be extended to integrate what is missing at the moment and to include if possible the use phase.

GOAL OF THE STUDY

The overall goal is the assessment throughout the application of the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) of the environmental and social risks associated with the production of 1 (one) Printed Circuit Board (PCB) containing an indium antimonide (InSb) chip, as part of the final Current Limiter (CL) device to be developed within the Novetrol project.

The focus is on the production process, which is reflected in the functional unit and its reference flow:

“manufacturing and production of printed circuit board containing InSb chip with the technical specifications required to be integrated within the current limiter device (CL) developed within the NOVETROL project”.

The reference flow in this case is equal to 1 item.

Furthermore, the study explores a lab-scale production in 2025, in Europe, a sensitivity analysis concerning the geographical location of suppliers, and a scenario evaluation at 2030. The system boundaries reflect the FU, including all the “cradle-to-gate” processes, and excluding what comes after the production of the PCB, as it would need to be integrated within the CL, its use phase and end-of-life.

The study excludes the production of capital goods and pieces of equipment required during the production/manufacturing of the PCB, as well as the waste management.

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE MANUFACTURING PROCESS AND MATERIAL AND ENERGY INVENTORY

Within the Novetrol project, the Silicon Austria Labs (SAL) is in charge of designing, manufacturing and testing the PCB with the InSb chip.

Data were collected from SAL throughout a Life Cycle data collection sheet, reviewed with the team and then employed in the modelling of both S-LCA and LCA models.

The following process flow reports the main steps of the laboratory production, together with the inputs required and outputs.

Figure 2 Process flow diagram concerning the PCB manufacturing at lab-scale. Source of data SAL. [Hasnaningrum H., 2025].

Qualitative information concerning the materials and energy consumption, as well as the supplier location, were collected. It was assumed that all the electricity required was supplied from the national grid mix (Austria) and the waste was assumed to be managed by Austria's waste management system.

Table 1 and Table 2 report materials and energy inputs, and wastes produced during the manufacturing process in 2025.

Table 1 Materials and energy required at the laboratory scale in 2025. Data provided by SAL.

Name of Process	Inputs	Quantity	Unit	Location
Photoresist coating	Photoresist nLoF 2020	0.002	l	Germany
	InSb wafer	0.007	kg	USA
	Electricity	1.07	kWh	Austria
Photolithography exposure	Electricity	1.53	kWh	Austria
Photoresist development	AZ 726 MIF developer	0.1	l	Germany
	Deionized water	0.1	l	Austria
Metal layer deposition	Ti pellets	0.0001	kg	France

	Au pellets	0.002	kg	France
	Electricity	5.39	kWh	Austria
Photoresist removal	DMSO	0.1	l	Germany
Rinse, dry, and dice	Deionized water	0.1	l	Austria
Integration in PCB	PCB	0.03	kg	Germany
	Solder paste	0.002	kg	Germany
	Electricity	0.48	kWh	Austria

Table 2 Waste output at laboratory scale in 2025. Data provided by SAL.

Name of Process	Waste Type	Quantity (kg)
Photoresist coating	Cleanroom compatible tissues contaminated with photoresist	0.005
	Excessive photoresist	0.001014
Photoresist development	Developer carrying photoresist	0.1
	Deionized water used in cleaning	0.1
Photoresist removal	DMSO carrying photoresist and metal	0.11
Rinse, dry, and dice	InSb shards	0.001
	Deionized water	0.1

Information reported in these 2 tables were used together with others in modelling the “baseline” represented by a production at laboratory scale in 2025.

A sensitivity analysis based on the change of geographical location of certain suppliers, based on the selection of the most probable supplier to be employed in a production at industrial scale, has been carried out for both S-LCA and LCA case studies. The quantities of inputs and FU were kept the same as in 2025 baseline scenario, while the origin of materials were varied based on the biggest exporter of those materials in 2024. The biggest exporters were identified by tracking the material through UN Comtrade database (comtrade.un.org) by its corresponding Harmonized System (HS) code (Table 3), which is an internationally standardised numerical method to classify traded products. Hence, it was possible to identify the key players for each material and to establish alternative sourcing scenarios for the sensitivity analysis.

Table 3 HS codes for the input materials.

Material input	HS Code	Description
Photoresist nLoF 2020	370710	Photographic goods: sensitized emulsions, put up in measured portions or put up for retail sale in a form ready for use
InSb wafer	381800	Chemical elements; doped for use in electronics, in the form of discs, wafers, or similar forms; chemical compounds doped for use in electronics
AZ 726 MIF developer	370790	Photographic goods: chemical preparations other than sensitized emulsions, put up in measured portions or put up for retail sale in a form ready for use
Deionised water	285300	Inorganic compounds (including distilled or conductivity water and water of similar purity); liquid air (rare gases

		removed or not); compressed air; amalgams, other than precious metal amalgams
Ti pellets	810890	Titanium; other than unwrought
Au pellets	710813	Metals: gold, semi manufactured
DMSO	29309	Organo-Sulphur compounds
I water	285300	Inorganic compounds (including distilled or conductivity water and water of similar purity); liquid air (rare gases removed or not); compressed air; amalgams, other than precious metal amalgams
PCB	8534	Circuits; printed
Solder paste	38101	Pickling preparations for metal surfaces; soldering, brazing or welding powders and pastes consisting of metal and other materials

The list of most probable suppliers at an industrial scale is reported in Table 4.

Table 4 Geographical locations employed in both the baseline case and the sensitivity analysis

Name of process	Inputs	Location	
		Baseline 2025	Sensitivity Analysis
Photoresist coating	Photoresist nLoF 2020	Germany	China
	InSb wafer	USA	China
Photoresist development	AZ 726 MIF developer	Germany	Japan
	Deionized water	Austria	Austria
Metal layer deposition	Ti pellets	France	China
	Au pellets	France	UK
Photoresist removal	DMSO	Germany	China
Rinse, dry and dice	Deionized water	Austria	Austria
Integration in PCB	PCB	Germany	China
	Solder paste	Germany	Hungary
Electricity production	-----	Austria	Austria
Waste management	-----	Austria	Austria

A future scenario concerning the production in 2030 of the item under study was developed. It was assumed that the supply chain would be the same as the baseline; the Functional Unit is adjusted based on projected number of current limiter devices required in 2030. In this case the study tries to envisage the absolute impact that would arise in the EU market due to the potential market request. The scenario is determined based on the projected use cases of the CL device as planned by the Novetrol project. The potential market demand has been estimated considering items directly integrated into LVDC microgrids, with a number of around 525000 items. In addition, a manufacturing optimization was assumed by applying an energy efficiency factor and the resources utilization. An assumption regarding the efficiency of material consumption was applied to the use of Photoresist nLoF 2020 during the photoresist coating process, with efficiency rate of 40%. The energy efficiency target set by

the EU envisages a minimum reduction equal to 11.7% in 2030 (European Commission, n.d.) compared to the consumption in 2025.

Table 5 Materials and energy requirements that are estimated to be required to produce 1 item in 2030

Name of Process	Inputs	Quantity	Unit
Photoresist coating	Photoresist nLoF 2020	0.0016	l
	InSb wafer	0.007	kg
	Electricity	0.94	kWh
Photolithography exposure	Electricity	1.35	kWh
Photoresist development	AZ 726 MIF developer	0.1	l
	Deionized water	0.1	l
Metal layer deposition	Ti pellets	0.0001	kg
	Au pellets	0.002	kg
	Electricity	4.76	kWh
Photoresist removal	DMSO	0.1	l
Rinse, dry, and dice	Deionized water	0.1	l
Integration in PCB	PCB	0.03	kg
	solder paste	0.002	kg
	Electricity	0.42384	kWh

Table 6 Waste outputs arising from the process.

Name of process	Waste Type	Quantity (kg)
Photoresist coating	Cleanroom compatible tissues contaminated with photoresist	0.005
	Excessive photoresist	0.0006084
Photoresist development	Developer carrying photoresist	0.1
	Deionized water used in cleaning	0.1
Photoresist removal	DMSO carrying photoresist and metal	0.11
Rinse, dry, and dice	InSb shards	0.001
	Deionized water	0.1

SOCIAL-LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT (S-LCA) – CASE STUDY

As broadly explained in D5.1, Social-Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) is a methodological framework designed to evaluate social and socio-economic risks, assess corporate social performance, and identify both positive and negative impacts arising from a product system’s activities and stakeholder interactions. A key outcome of S-LCA studies is the identification of social hotspots—areas within the life cycle where social issues are most likely to occur. These hotspots highlight regions or processes where social controversies or challenges are concentrated. The overarching objective of S-LCA is to enhance the socio-economic conditions of stakeholders who are directly or indirectly involved throughout the product life cycle. (Arcese et al., 2017; UNEP, 2020; Zamagni et al., 2015).

A “social risk” is defined as a “social topic for which an adverse impact is probable”, whilst a “social hotspot” is defined as a “location and/or activity in the life cycle where a social issue (as impact) and/or social risk is likely to occur”(UNEP, 2020). Based on this definition this case study aim to evaluate the potential social risks and identify the social hotspots associated with the supply-chain of the PCB to be employed within the CL device.

Social risks are evaluated for category of stakeholders, represented by all those actors in the value chain of the product that may be affected by the activities taking place along the whole life cycle of the product or service under evaluation. There are different categories of stakeholders:

- Workers;
- Communities;
- Governments;
- Consumers;
- Children, etc.

For each stakeholder category, there is one or more impact category and subcategories. For instance, for the workers category, there are different social issues to be associated with, like labour rights and health and safety. Each one of these can be expressed by different subcategories, for instance the labour right category can be sub-divided in different issues, such as the minimum salary, daily working hours, forced labour, etc.

For this specific case study it was decided to consider the stakeholders category, impact category and sub-categories reported in

Table 7 Stakeholder categories, impact categories and sub-categories selected for the case study.

Stakeholders	Impact Categories	Sub-categories
Local communities	Local employment	<i>Unemployment</i>
	Migration	<i>International migrant stock</i>
		<i>International migrant workers (in the sector/site)</i>
		<i>Migration flows</i>
		<i>Net migration</i>
Respect of indigenous rights	<i>Indigenous rights</i>	
Safe and healthy living conditions	<i>Drinking water coverage</i>	
	<i>Sanitation coverage</i>	
Society	Contribution to economic development	<i>Contribution of the sector to economic development</i>
		<i>Expenditures on education</i>
		<i>Illiteracy, female</i>
		<i>Illiteracy, male</i>
		<i>Illiteracy, total</i>
		<i>Value added (total)</i>
		<i>Youth illiteracy, female</i>
		<i>Youth illiteracy, male</i>
		<i>Youth illiteracy, total</i>
		<i>Global peace index</i>
Health and Safety	<i>Health expenditure</i>	
	<i>Life expectancy at birth</i>	
	<i>Active involvement of enterprises in corruption and bribery</i>	
Value Chain Actors	Corruption	<i>Public sector corruption</i>
	Fair competition	<i>Anti-competitive behaviour or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation</i>
	Promoting social responsibility	<i>Promoting social responsibility</i>
Workers	Child labour	<i>Child Labour, female</i>
		<i>Child Labour, male</i>
		<i>Child Labour, total</i>
	Discrimination	<i>Gender wage gap</i>
		<i>Men in the sectoral labour force</i>
		<i>Women in the sectoral labour force</i>
	Fair Salary	<i>Fair Salary</i>
	Forced Labour	<i>Frequency of forced labour</i>
		<i>Goods produced by forced labour</i>
		<i>Trafficking in persons</i>
Freedom of association and collective bargaining	<i>Association and bargaining rights</i>	
	<i>Trade unionism</i>	
Health and Safety	<i>DALYs(Disability-Adjusted Life years) due to indoor and outdoor air and water pollution</i>	

	<i>Fatal accidents</i>
	<i>Non-fatal accidents</i>
	<i>Safety measures</i>
	<i>Workers affected by natural disasters</i>
Social benefits, legal issues	<i>Social security expenditures</i>
	<i>Violations of employment laws and regulations</i>
Working time	<i>Weekly hours of work per employee</i>

It was decided to consider all the stakeholder categories, impact categories and sub-categories proposed by the PSILCA database (GreenDelta, 2020) as the study aim to study a low TRL product and identify the probable social hotspots in the life cycle of the product.

To be able to perform the study, it is important in S-LCA to define the activity variable, which is a measure of the process output. Each process has its own activity variable that is scaled to the activity variable of the whole system. This is usually defined either in working hours or value added. Worker-hours is the most commonly used activity variable, and it gives the number of worker-hours required to complete a production activity/unit process. The value-added activity variable, instead, considers the amount of the added value created in each process.

In this study, we employed the PSILCA database based on the value added activity variable. Therefore, all the material and energy information reported in section “Brief description of the manufacturing process and material and energy inventory” have been converted to “value added” activity variable in order to perform the S-LCA study.

A further data collection was carried out concerning the material prices from publicly available market sources. Prices were used as proxies for monetary input estimation, acknowledging that they may not fully reflect the actual procurement costs. The resulting monetary inputs were then calculated by combining these prices with the corresponding inventory quantities, forming the basis for scaling social risks in PSILCA.

Since not all material prices were reported in USD, they were converted to USD using the exchange rate prevailing at the time of data collection. Material prices were collected on 3 August 2025, and the conversion rate of €1 = \$1.159 USD was applied (Exchange Rates UK, 2025).

Table 8 Materials, energy and waste management prices employed to convert materials and energy and quantities into activity variables.

Name of process	Inputs	Amount	Unit	Source
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Photoresist coating	Photoresist nLoF 2020	692.0	USD/l	MicroChemicals (2025)
	InSb wafer	324,000.0	USD/kg	MTI Corporation (2025)
Photoresist development	AZ 726 MIF developer	84.5	USD/l	ConRo (2025)
	Deionized water	32.8	USD/l	Fisher Scientific (2025b)
Metal layer deposition	Ti pellets	8287.8	USD/kg	MaTeck GmbH (2025)
	Au pellets	107,419.3	USD/lg	World Bank (2025)
Photoresist removal	DMSO	146.7	USD/l	Fisher Scientific (2025a)
Rinse, dry and dice	Deionized water	32.8	USD/l	Fisher Scientific (2025b)
Integration in PCB	PCB	1291.7	USD/kg	Best Technology (2025) Technology (2025)
	Solder paste	283.9	USD/kg	Farnell (2025)
Electricity		0.31	USD/kWh	Statistic Austria (2025)
Waste		0.035	USD/kg	Ettlinger & Bapasola (2016)

MODELLING AND RESULTS

The S-LCIA was carried out to evaluate the potential social risks linked to the supply chain of the CL device. The modelling and results estimation was done using OpenLCA (v. 2.3.0) together with PSILCA database, which enables to quantify social risks across selected stakeholder groups, including local communities, value chain actors, society, and workers.

A cut-off criterion of 1E-5 mid risk working hours was applied to exclude negligible values from the assessment. The type of assessment applied was the social risk-based approach, implemented through the PSILCA Social Impacts Weighting Method, which translates sector and country-specific social risks into quantitative risk hours (Loubert et al., 2023).

Figure 3 Screenshot of the baseline system model created in OpenLCA (version 2.3).

RESULTS

Overall results are presented in Table 9.

For the baseline case, most of the material inputs are sourced from Europe. Meanwhile, in the sensitivity analysis, the supply chain was modelled based on the biggest key players of the supplied materials, which are mainly located in China and East Asia. The highest social risk is generated by the process of photoresist coating, followed by metal layer deposition and integration in PCB processes respectively. Regarding the overall social risk, sensitivity analysis resulted in a higher risk than the baseline. Material sources that mostly come from Asia have a social risk equals to 177,150 medium risk hours, whilst the baseline, where the inputs generally come from Europe, has an overall social risk equals to 71,351 medium risk hours.

This result indicates that the higher social risk in sensitivity analysis is likely caused by differences in labor conditions and economic development. Materials from Asia, specifically from China and Japan, have higher social risks because of longer working hours, lower wages, and less strong labor rights compared to Europe (Eurofound, 2019; You Xiaoying, 2025). Also, in some social categories such as health and safety, contribution to economic development, and social benefits, legal issues use percentage of GDP as a proxy to estimate the potential social risk (Loubert et al., 2023). In fact, GDP in East Asia, where China and Japan are located, has lower GDP than Europe. In April 2025, GDP in East Asia was reported to be 26.46 thousand USD, while GDP in Europe was reported 27.87 thousand USD (International Monetary Fund,

2025). Hence, the higher social risks in the sensitivity analysis for materials from Asia are caused by the combination of less favorable labor conditions and lower economic development. This shows that even if the processes are similar, the origin of materials has a big impact on the total social risk in the supply chain.

Table 9 Overall social risk of each process corresponding to the Baseline (laboratory scale 2025); sensitivity analysis based on the location of supplier, and finally the optimised process with a different FU (EU level).

Stakeholders	Photoresist coating	Photolithography exposure	Photoresist development	Metal layer deposition	Photoresist removal	Rinse, dry, and dice	Integration in PCB
BASELINE: Laboratory scale in 2025							
UNIT Mid Risk Hours							
Local Community	5.46E+03	1.73E+00	4.86E+01	6.31E+02	6.49E+01	1.15E+01	1.94E+02
Society	8.22E+03	1.02E+00	4.37E+01	9.34E+02	5.87E+01	1.01E+01	1.14E+02
Value Chain Actor	1.40E+04	2.18E+00	3.87E+01	9.31E+02	4.97E+01	1.04E+01	1.31E+02
Worker	3.77E+04	3.80E+00	8.89E+01	2.05E+03	1.14E+02	2.35E+01	4.16E+02
TOTAL	6.54E+04	8.74E+00	2.20E+02	4.55E+03	2.88E+02	5.55E+01	8.55E+02
SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS OF SUPPLY CHAIN							
UNIT Mid Risk Hours							
Local Community	3.40E+04	1.67E+00	1.41E+02	6.12E+02	2.29E+02	1.06E+01	5.84E+02
Society	1.58E+04	9.49E-01	7.01E+01	8.86E+02	1.07E+02	8.91E+00	2.73E+02
Value Chain Actor	1.40E+04	2.14E+00	8.93E+01	1.22E+03	1.39E+02	9.74E+00	2.40E+02
Worker	1.39E+05	3.68E+00	5.48E+02	1.49E+03	9.22E+02	2.17E+01	2.38E+03
TOTAL	2.03E+05	8.44E+00	8.49E+02	4.21E+03	1.40E+03	5.09E+01	3.47E+03
2030 SCENARIO							
UNIT Mid Risk Hours							
Local Community	2.67E+09	7.49E+05	2.45E+07	3.21E+08	3.27E+07	5.77E+06	4.56E+07
Society	4.04E+09	4.37E+05	2.15E+07	4.77E+08	2.89E+07	4.99E+06	2.56E+07
Value Chain Actor	7.09E+09	9.54E+05	1.96E+07	4.82E+08	2.52E+07	5.26E+06	3.11E+07
Worker	1.89E+10	1.65E+06	4.43E+07	1.05E+09	5.70E+07	1.17E+07	9.67E+07
TOTAL	3.27E+10	3.79E+06	1.10E+08	2.33E+09	1.44E+08	2.78E+07	1.99E+08

Figure 4 showcases the percentage contribution of each process to the social risks associated with each stakeholders category. The most affected stakeholder groups are workers, followed by the value chain actor, local community, and society respectively. For example, in the photoresist coating process, workers contribute with 58% of medium risk hours, while value chain actor, local community, and society contribute with 21%, 8%, 13% respectively. It can be noted that across all processes, worker is constantly representing the largest share of social risk. It is indicated that labor-related issues are the most critical impact along the supply chain. Other than that, value chain actor is the second most affected stakeholder with the highest social risk generated by photoresist coating process (25%). Local community and society have

lower contributions in most processes. However, they still cannot be neglected as they have some contributions to the overall social risk.

Figure 4 BASELINE: Social risks analysis concerning the stakeholder groups.

Figure 5 Sensitivity analysis: Social risks analysis concerning the stakeholder groups.

Figure 5 represents the result of different supply chains against the stakeholder groups. Similar with the baseline, the workers category is still becoming the most affected stakeholder, holding the largest share across all processes. However, differently from the baseline, the second most impacted stakeholder is local community. This difference is mainly because, in the sensitivity analysis, the materials such as InSb wafer, PCB, and some chemical products are coming from China, where social risks related to the local community stakeholder are higher. Value chain actors and society have lower contributions compared to workers and local community, but still represent important components of the overall social risk. It is

noteworthy to say that material sources from different regions can change the distribution of social impact across stakeholder groups.

Figure 6 Social risks estimated in 2030.

Lastly, the results on stakeholder groups of the prospective scenario can be seen in Figure 6. Like the other cases, worker remains to be the most affected stakeholder across all processes, with contributions ranging from 40% to 58%. In this case, photoresist coating contributes to the largest share in the worker stakeholder, followed by integration in PCB and metal layer deposition. These results are expected because the main materials, such as InSb wafers used in the photoresist coating process and PCB used in the integration in PCB process, dominate the social risk contribution. The system optimization in this case mainly targeted photoresist utilization efficiency and energy consumption efficiency, without changing the use of key materials such as PCB and InSb wafers. These results indicate that social risks are largely driven by the main material inputs and their supply chains, while improvements in material or energy efficiency have a limited effect on the distribution of social risks, based on the assumptions made in this case study.

LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT (LCA) – CASE STUDY

The Life Cycle Assessment is an internationally recognized methodology that enables the estimation of potential environmental impacts along the life cycle of products and/or services. It can be employed for different purposes, such as to understand the environmental impact of products already in the market, comparative studies, and to explore what would be the impact of emerging products with a low TRL. In this last case, LCA is useful to highlight possible issues and trade-off that may not be evident till the product is on the market.

In this case, we employ LCA to explore the potential environmental impact that arise when producing the PCB to be integrated within the CL when the production is at laboratory scale, then based on the S-LCA, a sensitivity analysis based on the geography is carried out, together with an estimation of the potential environmental impact due to the estimated EU market demand in 2030.

As explained in the section “CASE STUDY DEFINITION – GOAL AND SCOPE”, the functional unit for the baseline is equal to 1 item, the system boundaries are defined “cradle-to-gate”, in the future they will be expanded to include the use phase as well.

To align the S-LCA and LCA results, it was decided to leave out the study, at this point of the project development, some activities and or processes, these are:

- Transportation from the supplier to the production site (in Austria);
- Production and disposal of the packaging.

The modelling was carried out in SimaPro software using the database ecoinvent (vv. 3.10) (Wernet et al., 2016). The impact categories investigated are listed in Table 10 and the calculation method selected is the Environmental Footprint (vv.3.1) (Andreas Bassi et al., 2023; EC-JRC, 2012; Zampori & Pant, 2019) .

Table 10 List of the impact categories investigated in this LCA study.

Impact category	Unit
<i>Acidification</i>	mol H+ eq
<i>Climate change</i>	kg CO2 eq
<i>Ecotoxicity, freshwater</i>	CTUe
<i>Particulate matter</i>	disease inc.

<i>Eutrophication, marine</i>	kg N eq
<i>Eutrophication, freshwater</i>	kg P eq
<i>Eutrophication, terrestrial</i>	mol N eq
<i>Human toxicity, cancer</i>	CTUh
<i>Human toxicity, non-cancer</i>	CTUh
<i>Ionising radiation</i>	kBq U-235 eq
<i>Land use</i>	Pt
<i>Ozone depletion</i>	kg CFC11 eq
<i>Photochemical ozone formation</i>	kg NMVOC eq
<i>Resource use, fossils</i>	MJ
<i>Resource use, minerals and metals</i>	kg Sb eq
<i>Water use</i>	m3 depriv.

RESULTS

Results are presented for the production at laboratory scale for one InSb PCB device to be integrated within the Novetrol Current Limiter device. Table 11 presents the results in absolute values for each impact category and for each lab manufacturing steps. Wastes from lab are considered as hazardous wastes undergoing incineration. The assembly process, which is the last one, includes only electricity. For a quicker understanding of the results, Figure 7 presents a contribution analysis, that help to understand how much (in %) each process contributes to a specific environmental impact category.

Table 11 Absolute results from the LCIA for the laboratory production of 1 InSb PCB to be integrated within the Novetrol Current Limiter device

Impact category	Unit	Total	Assembly	Photoresist coating	Photolithography Exposure	Photoresist Development	Metal layer deposition	Photoresist Removal	Rinse, dry and dice
Acidification	mol H+ eq	1,00E+00	2,04E-03	8,25E-03	6,50E-03	3,33E-05	9,06E-01	1,77E-03	8,43E-07
Climate change	kg CO2 eq	1,14E+02	4,45E-01	1,31E+00	1,42E+00	9,07E-03	1,01E+02	1,91E-01	7,88E-05
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	9,34E+03	1,04E+00	4,01E+01	3,33E+00	1,70E-01	8,76E+03	2,30E+02	1,00E-02
Particulate matter	disease inc.	7,54E-06	3,30E-09	3,39E-08	1,05E-08	3,10E-10	6,93E-06	1,11E-08	6,71E-12
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	2,50E-01	4,80E-04	1,98E-03	1,53E-03	1,61E-05	2,32E-01	1,08E-04	6,73E-08
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	3,81E-01	7,27E-04	1,96E-03	2,32E-03	2,41E-06	3,61E-01	3,81E-05	3,42E-08
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N eq	2,91E+00	3,75E-03	1,98E-02	1,19E-02	8,20E-05	2,72E+00	1,10E-03	6,60E-07
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	9,45E-08	4,86E-11	1,27E-09	1,55E-10	4,32E-12	8,58E-08	4,94E-11	1,71E-13
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	6,86E-06	3,14E-09	5,07E-08	1,00E-08	7,16E-11	6,46E-06	1,37E-09	1,14E-12
Ionising radiation	kBq U-235 eq	1,20E+01	6,91E-04	5,77E-02	2,20E-03	1,13E-03	1,09E+01	1,75E-02	9,89E-06
Land use	Pt	9,79E+02	3,53E-01	2,97E+00	1,13E+00	3,20E-02	9,30E+02	3,55E-01	3,31E-04
Ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	1,41E-06	2,81E-09	1,00E-08	8,97E-09	6,11E-10	8,43E-07	1,34E-08	3,02E-11
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	7,14E-01	1,00E-03	5,19E-03	3,19E-03	3,44E-05	6,62E-01	7,23E-04	2,56E-07
Resource use, fossils	MJ	1,48E+03	4,70E+00	1,49E+01	1,50E+01	2,33E-01	1,32E+03	5,38E+00	1,04E-03
Resource use, minerals and metals	kg Sb eq	1,38E-01	3,03E-07	4,71E-03	9,66E-07	7,27E-08	1,29E-01	1,56E-06	1,03E-09
Water use	m3 depriv.	2,52E+01	2,96E-02	3,38E-01	9,44E-02	2,44E-03	2,27E+01	6,47E-02	8,79E-03

From the graph, it is easy to understand that the main contributor to most of the environmental impacts is represented by the metal layer deposition, which consists in the deposition of gold and titanium layers. It is interesting to notice that this process is the main contributor to all the impact categories. When the process is analyzed in more detail (Figure 8), one can observe that gold production is the main contributor.

The second element that contributes the most is the production of PCB. The third main contributor is represented by the photoresist coating, whilst almost all the others do not contribute significantly (less than 1%) to the environmental impacts.

Figure 7 Contribution analysis of each laboratory-scale manufacturing process.

Figure 8 Screenshot of the Sankey diagram representing the energy and material flows and their contribution percentage to the Climate Change impact category.

Table 12 and

Table 13 showcase results concerning an envisaged production at European level of around 524,504 InSb PCB to be integrated in the Current Limiter devices in 2030. Therefore, these results try to give an idea of the order of magnitude of the impact that could arise from mass production of these items.

From the results, the contribution of gold remains the same; indeed, the energy efficiency factor and the reduction of some chemicals are not relevant due to the significance of gold. It will be interesting to understand if gold will remain the main contributor to the environmental impact when the assessment will be extended to the Current Limiter device and to an use case-study.

The key message from this assessment is the relevance that some materials, even if used in very small quantities, have on the environment. It should be investigated if the gold used in the device can be recycled gold and whether the supplier of gold pellets for the electronic industry do use recycled gold.

Table 12 Results for the production of PCBs in Europe to satisfy the estimated demand in 2030.

Impact category	Unit	Total	Assembly	Photoresist coating	Photolithography Exposure	Photoresist Development	Metal layer deposition	Photoresist Removal	Rinse, dry and dice	Wastes	PCB
<i>Acidification</i>	mol H+ eq	5,25E+05	1,07E+03	4,05E+03	3,01E+03	1,75E+01	4,74E+05	9,30E+02	4,42E-01	5,82E+02	4,10E+04
<i>Climate change</i>	kg CO2 eq	5,93E+07	2,33E+05	6,24E+05	6,57E+05	4,76E+03	5,24E+07	1,00E+05	4,13E+01	5,29E+05	4,74E+06
<i>Ecotoxicity, freshwater</i>	CTUe	4,90E+09	5,48E+05	2,09E+07	1,54E+06	8,92E+04	4,60E+09	1,21E+08	5,25E+03	7,82E+06	1,51E+08
<i>Particulate matter</i>	disease inc.	3,95E+00	1,73E-03	1,73E-02	4,87E-03	1,62E-04	3,63E+00	5,81E-03	3,52E-06	6,28E-03	2,81E-01
<i>Eutrophication, marine</i>	kg N eq	1,31E+05	2,52E+02	9,71E+02	7,09E+02	8,45E+00	1,22E+05	5,65E+01	3,53E-02	1,44E+02	7,10E+03
<i>Eutrophication, freshwater</i>	kg P eq	1,99E+05	3,81E+02	9,27E+02	1,07E+03	1,27E+00	1,89E+05	2,00E+01	1,80E-02	1,57E+02	7,42E+03
<i>Eutrophication, terrestrial</i>	mol N eq	1,52E+06	1,96E+03	9,85E+03	5,53E+03	4,30E+01	1,42E+06	5,79E+02	3,46E-01	1,36E+03	7,72E+04
<i>Human toxicity, cancer</i>	CTUh	4,95E-02	2,55E-05	6,62E-04	7,18E-05	2,27E-06	4,50E-02	2,59E-05	8,95E-08	6,01E-04	3,15E-03
<i>Human toxicity, non-cancer</i>	CTUh	3,60E+00	1,65E-03	2,62E-02	4,64E-03	3,75E-05	3,39E+00	7,21E-04	5,96E-07	1,58E-03	1,75E-01
<i>Ionising radiation</i>	kBq U-235 eq	6,30E+06	3,62E+02	3,02E+04	1,02E+03	5,95E+02	5,69E+06	9,18E+03	5,19E+00	1,31E+04	5,56E+05
<i>Land use</i>	Pt	5,13E+08	1,85E+05	1,51E+06	5,22E+05	1,68E+04	4,88E+08	1,86E+05	1,73E+02	3,80E+05	2,26E+07
<i>Ozone depletion</i>	kg CFC11 eq	7,36E-01	1,48E-03	4,87E-03	4,16E-03	3,21E-04	4,40E-01	7,01E-03	1,58E-05	5,36E-03	2,73E-01
<i>Photochemical ozone formation</i>	kg NMVOC eq	3,74E+05	5,25E+02	2,59E+03	1,48E+03	1,81E+01	3,46E+05	3,79E+02	1,34E-01	5,60E+02	2,16E+04
<i>Resource use, fossils</i>	MJ	7,74E+08	2,47E+06	7,19E+06	6,94E+06	1,22E+05	6,90E+08	2,82E+06	5,43E+02	2,51E+06	6,20E+07
<i>Resource use, minerals and metals</i>	kg Sb eq	7,24E+04	1,59E-01	2,47E+03	4,47E-01	3,81E-02	6,78E+04	8,19E-01	5,43E-04	7,44E-01	2,08E+03
<i>Water use</i>	m3 depriv.	1,32E+07	1,55E+04	1,73E+05	4,37E+04	1,28E+03	1,19E+07	3,39E+04	4,61E+03	2,65E+04	9,72E+05

Table 13 Contribution of each process to the total value of each impact category.

Impact category	Unit	Assembl y	Photoresi st coating	Photolithography Exposure	Photoresist Development	Metal layer depositio n	Photoresi st Removal	Rinse, dry and dice	Waste s	PCB
Acidification	mol H+ eq	0,204%	0,772%	0,573%	0,003%	90,339%	0,177%	0,000%	0,111 %	7,821%
Climate change	kg CO2 eq	0,393%	1,052%	1,107%	0,008%	88,385%	0,169%	0,000%	0,891 %	7,994%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	0,011%	0,427%	0,031%	0,002%	93,824%	2,466%	0,000%	0,160 %	3,079%
Particulate matter	disease inc.	0,044%	0,438%	0,123%	0,004%	91,982%	0,147%	0,000%	0,159 %	7,103%
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	0,193%	0,742%	0,542%	0,006%	92,930%	0,043%	0,000%	0,110 %	5,433%
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	0,192%	0,466%	0,539%	0,001%	94,986%	0,010%	0,000%	0,079 %	3,728%
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N eq	0,129%	0,648%	0,364%	0,003%	93,654%	0,038%	0,000%	0,089 %	5,075%
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	0,052%	1,337%	0,145%	0,005%	90,836%	0,052%	0,000%	1,214 %	6,360%
Human toxicity, non- cancer	CTUh	0,046%	0,728%	0,129%	0,001%	94,163%	0,020%	0,000%	0,044 %	4,869%
Ionising radiation	kBq U-235 eq	0,006%	0,478%	0,016%	0,009%	90,325%	0,146%	0,000%	0,207 %	8,813%
Land use	Pt	0,036%	0,294%	0,102%	0,003%	95,052%	0,036%	0,000%	0,074 %	4,403%
Ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	0,200%	0,662%	0,564%	0,044%	59,786%	0,952%	0,002%	0,727 %	37,063%

Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	0,141%	0,693%	0,396%	0,005%	92,737%	0,102%	0,000%	0,150 %	5,778%
Resource use, fossils	MJ	0,319%	0,929%	0,897%	0,016%	89,138%	0,365%	0,000%	0,325 %	8,011%
Resource use, minerals and metals	kg Sb eq	0,000%	3,411%	0,001%	0,000%	93,707%	0,001%	0,000%	0,001 %	2,879%
Water use	m3 depriv.	0,118%	1,313%	0,332%	0,010%	90,360%	0,257%	0,035%	0,201 %	7,374%

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